

Author alphabetization is racist

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Abstract

Economists are gradually abandoning the norm of listing authors alphabetically, but not everyone is convinced that alphabetical discrimination is a serious problem. This article contributes further evidence that author alphabetization should be abandoned by demonstrating that alphabetical discrimination is also racist discrimination. 65.0% of Black, 64.5% of White, 62.7% of Other, 60.4% of Hispanic, and 54.6% of Asian Americans have a Last Name First Initial (LNFI) that is before N, the halfway point in the alphabet. In a random two-person team of one White and one Asian-American, with author alphabetization there is a simulated 45% chance of an Asian first author, 5% fewer percentage points than random assignment. Previous literature documents the negative career consequences in the economics profession of appearing later in the alphabet.

Keywords: Alphabetical discrimination, scientometrics, co-authorship, informetrics, academic outcomes.

JEL classification: A12, A14, N01

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1 Introduction

With each passing decade, fewer economists are following the norm of author alphabetization (Wohlrabe and Bornmann, 2022), including several notable Nobel prize-winning economists. The principal argument for author alphabetization is that having a standard procedure reduces conflict among coauthors for first authorship. However, evidence has accumulated that author alphabetization has unintended side-effects.

In most academic fields, first authorship is given to the principal investigator. As such, first authorship is highly regarded in adjacent fields in which economists could be employed. Additionally, industry positions may require first authorships. Thus, the system of author alphabetization self-imposes friction upon economists' own labor mobility, at least if their Last Name First Initial (LNFI) is late in the alphabet (Ong, Chan, Torgler, and Yang, 2018). One could argue these unfortunate spillover effects on some economists are worth the trade-off, if author alphabetization at least works well within academic economics.

But there is evidence that author order matters even among economists who should know better. Einav and Yariv (2006) found that economists with a LNFI early in the alphabet were more likely to receive tenure at top faculties, contrary to psychologists who do not practice author alphabetization. Efthyvoulou (2008) replicates the advantage of LNFIs early in the alphabet within economics. Kadel and Walter (2015) found that economists with a LNFI late in the alphabet strategically publish solo or in pairs, to avoid being lumped in an "et al." Li and Yi (2021) found that Chinese economists with a LNFI late in the alphabet are more likely to work in China, where author alphabetization is not common, than their similarly-named Chinese peers in other academic disciplines. Weber (2018) provides a literature review of the empirical evidence surrounding author alphabetization.

Recognizing that different ethnic groups have different frequency distributions of LNFIs, the present research continues this literature by using a recent publicly available name dictionary from the United States (Imai, Olivella, and Rosenman, 2022). Specifically, if it is such that a person's ethnicity can predict their last name's first initial, and thus their order in an alphabetized list, then institutionalized author alphabetization may unintentionally favor some ethnic groups over others.

2 Methods

The data used to estimate LNFI distribution is the publicly accessible "Race and ethnicity data for first, middle, and last names" version 9.0 from the Harvard Dataverse (Imai, Olivella, and Rosenman, 2022), which was the latest available version at the time of writing. This dataset pairs the 338,000 last names of 36,000,000 individuals with self-reported race and ethnicity for five categories: White, Black, Hispanic, Asian, and Other. A discrete distribution of LNFI can be created using the "P(last name | race)" dataset by taking the first initial of

each last name.

Imai, Olivella, and Rosenman (2022) defend this dataset as the cleanest available, though it comes with two serious limitations for the present work, which I will address here. First, while the United States is a multi-ethnic country, this database does not in fact reflect the true probability distribution of last names in the world (nor that of economists). Second, last names with fewer than 25 appearances are removed from the database for privacy purposes, a decision which disproportionately affects smaller ethnic groups.

The first problem is simply a limitation of this study. I assume that this LNFI data from the United States is at least suggestive of the true underlying worldwide LNFI distribution (or that of economists). However, this limits only the trustworthiness of the precise numbers in this analysis, not the general conclusion. Not every language even has every letter present in the Latin script; under these conditions, alphabetical discrimination is unavoidable *a priori*. If it is not an ethnic group that is affected, then it is a nationality or a linguistic family – equally unacceptable forms of discrimination. However, the second limitation implies that the smaller ethnic groups are represented less frequently in the data by construction, and therefore a correction must be applied before comparisons can be made. Because of the privacy concern, only 97.3% of Black-, 97.1% of White-, 91.7% of Other-, 90.7% of Asian-, and 89.1% of Hispanic-Americans are represented in the dataset. Because it is not possible to know the LNFI distribution of whatever names were omitted, I set the total percentage observed equal to 100% for each ethnic group and transform the values associated with each letter proportionally. This is mathematically equivalent to finding a constant such that the product of the total percentage for a given ethnicity and this constant equals 100%, then multiplying each of the individual letters by this constant. Reacting in this manner assumes the omitted names are distributed similarly to the observed distribution. This is the "proportional specification." A robustness test is performed in which the remainder of 100% and the total percentage for a given ethnicity is spread evenly throughout the letters (A and B as well as Q and X), but this alternative specification does not change the interpretation of the results. This is the "equal-weighted specification."

3 Results

The discrete distribution of last name first initials by race is summarized in Figure 1. In this figure, the X axis represents a sequential increase in the letters in the alphabet (the first 1, 2, 3, ... up to all 26 letters of the alphabet), while the Y axis represents the percentage of individuals represented by the given subset of letters. On the left of the graph at 0 letters, 0.0% of each ethnic group is represented; while on the right of the graph at all 26 letters, 100.0% of each ethnic group is represented. In the middle of the graph, each ethnic group has been plotted to visualize how each additional letter describes a differing percentage of each of the five ethnic groups, Black-, White-, Hispanic-, Asian-,

Figure 1: The distribution of the Last Name First Initials (LNFIs) among Americans.

and Other-Americans. Asian-Americans, in blue, noticeably lag behind the rest of the ethnic groups in the first half of the alphabet. For precision, the exact values used to create this discrete distribution are reported in Table 1.

The values in Table 1 can equally be used to simulate the likelihood that a random pairing of two authors, one White- and one Asian-American, would have an Asian-American first author. In a randomly seeded Monte Carlo simulation of 50,000 random author pairings (in which ties are randomly broken), Asian-American authors are first authors only 45% of the time. This is significantly less than the 50-50 chance of randomly assigned author orders. The values in Table 1 indicate that White- and Black-Americans have roughly similar LNFI distributions, while Hispanic- and Other-Americans tend to lag behind these groups, with Asian-Americans far behind. To make the replication of these results fast and easy, the R code used to generate Figure 1, Table 1, and the Monte Carlo simulation is made publicly available here: [10.5281/zenodo.12536729](https://zenodo.org/record/12536729).

4 Discussion

This analysis establishes that author alphabetization is an institutionally racist practice. Author alphabetization systematically favors some ethnic groups, notably White-Americans, and disfavors others, notably Asian-Americans. Previous research has demonstrated that alphabetical discrimination within economics is already problematic because it is arbitrary and has perverse effects on the field (Einav and Yariv, 2006; Kadel and Walter, 2015; Li and Yi, 2021). The present work extends these findings by showing that, on top of being arbitrary and perverse, author alphabetization is racist.

5 Conclusion

I assume that the practice of author alphabetization was established in good faith and for good reason, and following this rule in the past does not make a scientist racist. The trailblazers of author alphabetization likely just did not consider a world in which tens of millions of people are named Nguyen, Singh, Wang, and Zhang.

To maintain the current, conflict-free status quo among coauthors, another standardized and externally-verifiable system must take its place. The alternative is obvious and easy. Journals can randomize author order. Certain economics journals already impose author alphabetization; they can just as easily impose author randomization. In this alternative, author order would be determined by the roll of an equally-weighted die by the neutral third-party journal, and any scientist could scrape author orders to verify that journals are indeed neutral third-parties. The (at least hypothetically) contribution-based system present in other fields may advantage scientists with age, seniority, rank, or sway within the institution. Alas, any non-randomized system can impose unintended consequences on people based on their demographics, an unacceptable

side effect for any scientific field.

Prior research has documented negative career consequences for economists with a LNFI late in the alphabet. Should committees award the best X's, Y's, and Z's? Does alphabetical discrimination merit *reparations*? Let us just get rid of this ridiculous precedent. This world is crazy enough as it is.

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Table 1: Two estimations of the distribution of the Last Name First Initials (LNFI) among Americans.

Letters	Proportional specification					Equal-weighted specification				
	White	Black	Hispanic	Asian	Other	White	Black	Hispanic	Asian	Other
1	3.16%	3.43%	6.38%	4.03%	5.04%	3.18%	3.44%	6.10%	4.01%	4.94%
2	12.99%	13.39%	11.23%	8.80%	13.21%	12.83%	13.23%	10.84%	8.70%	12.75%
3	20.80%	20.38%	20.79%	16.18%	20.44%	20.53%	20.14%	19.78%	15.75%	19.71%
4	25.68%	25.20%	25.27%	20.84%	25.43%	25.38%	24.93%	24.19%	20.34%	24.60%
5	27.57%	27.03%	26.89%	21.74%	27.16%	27.33%	26.82%	26.05%	21.51%	26.50%
6	31.11%	30.24%	30.57%	23.37%	30.24%	30.87%	30.04%	29.75%	23.34%	29.65%
7	36.10%	35.33%	39.06%	26.40%	35.26%	35.84%	35.10%	37.73%	26.45%	34.57%
8	43.90%	42.94%	42.52%	31.72%	41.39%	43.51%	42.61%	41.24%	31.63%	40.51%
9	44.29%	43.32%	43.09%	32.40%	42.03%	44.00%	43.08%	42.17%	32.61%	41.41%
10	46.95%	49.97%	44.41%	34.69%	45.49%	46.70%	49.66%	43.76%	35.04%	44.91%
11	50.33%	51.64%	44.87%	40.51%	48.77%	50.10%	51.38%	44.59%	40.68%	48.23%
12	55.08%	55.74%	49.57%	48.47%	53.49%	54.82%	55.48%	49.19%	48.25%	52.88%
13	64.51%	64.99%	60.45%	54.55%	62.74%	64.08%	64.58%	59.31%	54.13%	61.69%
14	66.18%	66.34%	62.13%	61.44%	65.03%	65.82%	66.00%	61.23%	60.74%	64.11%
15	67.49%	67.21%	64.67%	62.27%	66.34%	67.20%	66.95%	63.90%	61.85%	65.62%
16	72.61%	71.83%	70.97%	72.06%	72.42%	72.29%	71.55%	69.94%	71.09%	71.52%
17	72.78%	71.93%	71.66%	72.48%	72.70%	72.57%	71.75%	70.97%	71.83%	72.09%
18	77.85%	76.89%	83.20%	76.16%	78.66%	77.60%	76.68%	81.67%	75.52%	77.88%
19	87.74%	85.39%	90.37%	84.47%	88.20%	87.31%	85.05%	88.48%	83.41%	86.95%
20	91.37%	89.60%	93.33%	90.32%	91.92%	90.95%	89.26%	91.54%	89.08%	90.68%
21	91.58%	89.73%	93.71%	90.66%	92.15%	91.26%	89.49%	92.29%	89.74%	91.21%
22	92.74%	90.29%	98.31%	93.30%	93.87%	92.50%	90.14%	96.81%	92.50%	93.11%
23	99.08%	99.39%	99.02%	96.21%	98.68%	98.77%	99.09%	97.87%	95.49%	97.83%
24	99.08%	99.39%	99.03%	96.66%	98.73%	98.88%	99.20%	98.29%	96.26%	98.20%
25	99.60%	99.90%	99.25%	98.76%	99.46%	99.50%	99.80%	98.91%	98.52%	99.19%
26	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%